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ТЕОРЕТИЧНІ АСПЕКТИ СУМІСНОЇ ІНТЕРПРЕТАЦІЇ СЕЙСМО- ТА ГРАВИМЕТРИЧНИХ ДАНИХ В РАЙОНАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВНИХ НА НАФТОГАЗОНОСНОСТЬ

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THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF JOINT INTERPRETATION OF SEISMO- AND GRAVIMETRIC DATA IN AREAS PROSPECTED FOR OIL AND GAS POTENTIAL

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АНОТАЦІЯ

В статті розглядаються теоретичні аспекти постановки та розв'язання задачі сумісної інверсії у застосуванні до сейсмічних та гравіметричних даних на основі успішного досвіду цього підходу для інверсії одного типу даних.

В рамках імовірнісного підходу стандартна постановка сумісної інверсії геофізичних даних формулюється як задача максимізації апостеріорної умовної щільності ймовірності вектора модельних параметрів. У зв'язку зі складністю визначення цих функцій видається доцільним перетворити задачу максимізації на задачу мінімізації вектора багатоцільової функції. У цьому випадку апріорна інформація формалізується за допомогою нечітких множин. Розв'язок задачі мінімізації здійснюється за допомогою алгоритму пошуку Парето-оптимальних розв'язків.

ABSTRACT

This paper considers the theoretical aspects of the formulation and solution of the joint inversion problem as applied to seismic and gravimetric data, based on the successful experience of this approach for inversion of one data type.

Within the framework of the probabilistic approach, the standard formulation of the joint inversion of geophysical data is formulated as the problem of maximization a posteriori conditional probability density of the vector of model parameters. Due to the complexity of the definition of these functions, it seems expedient to transform the maximization problem into the problem of minimization the vector of multiobjective function. In this case, a priori information is formalized by means of fuzzy sets. The solution of the minimization problem is carried out using the search algorithm for Pareto-optimal solutions.

Ключові слова: сумісна інверсія, інтерпретація геофізичних даних, нечіткі множини, Парето-оптимальні розв'язки.

Keywords: joint inversion, interpretation geophysical data, fuzzy sets, Pareto-optimal solutions.

Introduction. Gravimetric survey is the most efficient and economical method for identifying deep structures, defining the boundaries of oil and gas bearing sedimentary basins, as well as discovering promising areas and detecting local structures in the form of potential oil and gas traps. Interpretation of gravity anomalies caused by possible oil and gas reservoirs is often carried out at the initial stage of exploration [2].

The traditional concept of oil and gas geology and the corresponding geophysical technologies and methods of prospecting for minerals are mainly focused on large areas of structural and non-structural deposits in the upper part of sedimentary complexes. Nevertheless, the development of small in area, but large in volume reserves, complexly constructed deposits in sedimentary, metamorphosed, volcanogenic and igneous complexes is one of the main reserves of long-term energy supply [1,9,10]. It is obvious that the efficiency of oil exploration in various regions depends both on the tools for modeling complex geological structures within the framework of the method used, and on the interpretation capabilities of the method itself. The effectiveness

of gravity exploration is based on the well-known works of V.I. Starostenko, E.G. Bulakh, V.M. Strakhov, A.I. Kobrunov and many others.

Due to the fact that oil and gas structures are a complex layered geological environment, it is not enough to use one method to identify them.

When studying deep-lying structural oil and gas fields by means of seismic exploration, the method of reflected waves is of primary importance. High resolution, which provides separate study of the section over a large number of reflecting horizons, makes the method of reflected waves indispensable in the search for small-sized structural objects occurring at great depths.

Today, it becomes obvious that there is no perfect method for interpreting geophysical data. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages, and at best, data from other methods is used as the end result of their interpretation. Therefore, it was logical that the idea of joint interpretation of geophysical data emerged, the development of which was initiated in the works [3, 4, 8].

At the moment, there is a sufficient theoretical base for the application of numerical methods of multi-objective optimization for the inversion of geophysical data of various types.

In this paper, we consider the theoretical aspects of formulation and solution the problem of joint inversion as applied to seismic and gravity data, based on the successful experience of such an approach for inversion of one type of data. Within the framework of the probabilistic approach, the standard formulation of the joint inversion of geophysical data is formulated as the problem of a posteriori maximization of the conditional density functions of the vector of model parameters. Due to the complexity of determining these functions, it seems expedient to transform the maximization problem into the problem of minimizing the vector of a multiobjective function. In this case, a priori information is formalized by means of fuzzy sets. The solution of the minimization problem is carried out using the search algorithm for Pareto-optimal solutions.

Joint interpretation of gravity and seismic data.

Joint interpretation of gravity and seismic data allows the use of useful information from each method. There are two possible ways to combine the data obtained from the two methods:

- the data of each method is inverted independently. The result of such a procedure is a set of different models, and the final solution is built using all independent models;
- a set of several data types is combined into one, which is subsequently subject to inversion. This procedure, called joint inversion of several data types, provides the final model directly.

The joint inversion problem is often formulated as a scalar one. The operators of the direct problem are linearized, and the data errors are considered random and follow a Gaussian distribution. This approach can be found in some authors [12,13,16]. But most geophysical inverse problems are non-linear, their solutions are not unique, and data errors are not always caused by random noise.

It is advisable to solve such problems within the framework of direct search methods, when the final solution is selected from a set of alternative solutions modeled in a parametric space under the control of certain rules [7, 15].

Consider the problem of joint data inversion of two seismic and gravimetric methods.

Formulation of the inverse problem of gravimetry using the ratio of velocity and density.

In the case of a linear problem, there is an attempt to use the density-velocity relationship as a case of statistical dependence. The idea of the method was proposed in the book by Karataev G.I. and Pashkevich I.K. [4] and further developed in [5]. The method is based on the concept of a geophysical body for which all relationships between physical parameters are established, in this case the relationship between seismic wave velocity and density, which mainly depends on PT (pressure and temperature). If only the P-wave ve-

locity is known, from a wide angle of reflection and refraction, the rock density $\rho(x, y, z)$ at some point can be estimated by the equation:

$$\rho(x, y, z) = a(x, y, z) + b(x, y, z) V_p(x, y, z), (x, y, z) \in T, \square$$

where $a(x, y, z), b(x, y, z)$ are unknown non-linear functions depending on pressure and temperature, rock composition and tectonic differences inside the body T , $V_p(x, y, z)$, is the velocity of longitudinal waves.

The proposed approach makes it possible to formulate the inverse problem as a linear one with a fixed and relatively small number of model parameters of the vector \mathbf{m} :

$$\mathbf{G}\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{d},$$

where \mathbf{G} is a matrix composed of the values of the linear operator of the direct problem at observation points, \mathbf{d} is the vector of observed gravity data. The least squares method gives good results and does not require a priori information about the dependence of density and velocity.

Standard formulation of the joint inversion problem based on a probabilistic approach.

The probabilistic approach to the inversion of geophysical data suggests the following formulation.

Let T be a geological object whose physical properties and shape can be described by a vector of parameters $\mathbf{m} = [m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n] \in M$, where M is the set of possible combinations of parameters defined in the parametric space R^n . Assume that independent a priori information about the object T can be expressed in terms of the probability density function (PDF) $p(\mathbf{m})$. Then the vector \mathbf{m} can be obtained as a result of the inversion of the observed data vector

$$\mathbf{d}_{obs} = (d_1, d_2, \dots, d_q),$$

where $d_i, i = \overline{1, q}$ are individual measurements. The inversion procedure maximizes a posteriori the conditional probability density of the vector \mathbf{m} [16]:

$$p(\mathbf{m} | \mathbf{d}_{obs}) = p(\mathbf{m})p(\mathbf{d}_{obs} | \mathbf{m})/p(\mathbf{d}_{obs}), \mathbf{m} \in M. (1)$$

where $p(\mathbf{m})$ – apriori PDF of the vector \mathbf{m} , $p(\mathbf{d}_{obs} | \mathbf{m})$ — conditional probability density of experimental data, $p(\mathbf{d}_{obs})$ – limiting probability density of experimental data. Since $p(\mathbf{d}_{obs})$ does not depend on \mathbf{m} , we can take it as some constant b . Then the maximum conditional PDF (1) gives an estimate of the parameters of the vector \mathbf{m} .

Suppose that k geophysical experiments are performed to obtain information about the object T . The results of these experiments form the vector

$$\mathbf{d}_{obs} = \{\mathbf{d}_{obs}^1, \mathbf{d}_{obs}^2, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{obs}^k\}. (2)$$

If all experiments were performed independently, then the errors in individual data sets are not correlated and all $d_{obs}^i, i = 1, \dots, k$ can be considered independent random variables. Then the a posteriori PDF of the parameter vector \mathbf{m} can be written [3]:

$$p(\mathbf{m} | d_{obs}^1, d_{obs}^2, \dots, d_{obs}^k) = bp(\mathbf{m})p_1(d_{obs}^1 | \mathbf{m})p_2(d_{obs}^2 | \mathbf{m}) \dots p_k(d_{obs}^k | \mathbf{m}), \mathbf{m} \in M. (3)$$

All PDF in (3) depend on one vector \mathbf{m} . Maximization (3) gives an estimate \mathbf{m}^* of the parameter vector \mathbf{m} , which is taken as a solution to the problem of joint inversion of several data types.

In many real problems, we can assume that all PDF $p(\mathbf{m})$ and $p_i(d_{obs}^i|\mathbf{m})$, $i = \overline{1, k}$ are Gaussian, then

$$L(\mathbf{m}) = \sum_{i=1}^k \left\| g_i(\mathbf{m}) - \mathbf{d}_{obs}^i \right\|_{l_{Q_i}} + \left\| \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_0 \right\|_{l_n}, \mathbf{m} \in M, \quad (4)$$

where $\left\| g_i(\mathbf{m}) - \mathbf{d}_{obs}^i \right\|_{l_{Q_i}}$ denotes the difference between the theoretically calculated and observed values in the weighted norm l_{Q_i} and $\left\| \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_0 \right\|_{l_n}$ is the difference between the desired model \mathbf{m} and the a priori \mathbf{m}_0 in the weighted norm l_n .

If all operators of direct problems are linear and the l_2 norm is used, then problem (4) can be solved by well-known methods of matrix inversion. Otherwise, linear inversion methods are not applicable, and the multivariate posterior PDF (3) must be analyzed to find a solution.

Description of uncertain a priori information.

Since the model space is usually multidimensional, the corresponding apriori distribution is, as a rule, rather complicated. If an explicit expression for the probability density is known, then it can be used in an analytical solution, although this is not always necessary. For example, when using Monte Carlo methods, it is sufficient to have only a set of probabilistic rules that allow the generation of model samples distributed according to the probability density function $p(\mathbf{m})$ in the model space [11].

On the other hand, uncertain a priori information can have an improbability character; it is often associated with inaccurate knowledge about the object under study. Then it makes sense to describe it formally using a non-probability measure of uncertainty, namely through fuzzy sets [17,18]. The theory of fuzzy sets is now a well-developed area of mathematics. We give only the definition of a fuzzy set:

Let U be the so-called universal set, from whose elements all other sets considered in this class of problems are formed. A fuzzy set A is a collection of pairs: $A = \left\{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in U \right\}$, where μ_A is the

$$F(\mathbf{m}) = [\mu_M(\mathbf{m}), p_1(d_{obs}^1|\mathbf{m}), p_2(d_{obs}^2|\mathbf{m}), \dots, p_k(d_{obs}^k|\mathbf{m})], \mathbf{m} \in M \quad (5)$$

This is the formulation of a multi-objective optimization problem (MOP). Such a problem can be defined as minimizing the objective function vector

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x})],$$

which takes values in the objective space R^k under the condition $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in X \subseteq R^n$, where X – the set of possible solutions MOP:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in X} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x})], \quad (6)$$

and the set of possible solutions is limited by the system of restrictions [14].

For efficient search in a multidimensional parametric space, the work [7] proposed a global optimization algorithm, the result of which is a set of Pareto-optimal solutions. The algorithm is based on the idea of approximating the parametric space by Voronoi diagrams, proposed by M. Sambridge [15]. The proposed

maximizing the function (3) is equivalent to minimizing the following function

membership function, i.e. $\mu_A : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$. The membership function is an analogue of the characteristic binary function in ordinary sets.

An important advantage is that the basic operations of fuzzy sets provide a fairly convenient combination of various precise and fuzzy constraints on model parameters. However, it must be remembered that the membership function cannot be used instead of a priori PDF in the classical formulation of the inverse problem, since they not only express two different types of uncertain information, but also correspond to different measures of uncertainty, which must satisfy different axioms. In order to combine different types of uncertainty in one inversion scheme, it is necessary to change the formulation of the inverse problem.

Joint inversion of several data types as a multi-objective optimization problem.

Let X be a fuzzy set of possible solutions defined in a parametric space with a membership function

$\mu_M(\mathbf{m})$ and $p_i(d_{obs}^i|\mathbf{m})$, $i = \overline{1, \dots, k}$ – be the conditional probability density functions of the experimental data. The function $\mu_M(\mathbf{m})$ determines the degree to which the parameter vector \mathbf{m} belongs to the set of possible solutions, which depends not only on experimental data, but also on a priori constraints.

Then the problem of joint inversion of several data types can be considered as a problem of simultaneous maximization of all conditional a posteriori PDF of the parameter vector \mathbf{m} in equation (3) and the membership function of the fuzzy set of possible solutions $\mu_M(\mathbf{m})$,

where $\mu_M(\mathbf{m}) = \max(\mu_M(m_i))$, $i = \overline{1, \dots, n}$.

This means that instead of the scalar function (3), the objective function vector is subject to maximization:

approach has been shown to be effective for inversion of seismic [8] and gravimetric [6] data.

When interpreting several types of data together, there may be cases where a set of complete optimal solutions does not exist. But the set of Pareto-optimal solutions and weakly Pareto-optimal solutions always exists. However, any Pareto-optimal solution is always a compromise of solutions. In other words, it is impossible to improve any solution from the Pareto set by reducing one objective function without increasing others. Since the number of trade-offs in a real MOP can be quite large, the set of Pareto-optimal solutions can contain various solutions with different trade-offs between different objectives. Thus, the trade-off analysis between the various components of the vector objective function is a necessary stage in the selection of final solutions from the Pareto set.

Conclusion. The problem of joint interpretation of geophysical data uniquely expands the possibilities of interpretation methods in the search for oil and gas fields. This paper touches upon a rather narrow theoretical question. In addition to the above, in each specific problem, a thorough analysis of the influence of errors on the quality of the set of possible solutions is required. Errors in experimental data and imprecise parameterization of the model destroy the overall optimal solution that usually exists for data without errors. As a result, the complete optimal solution expands to a large Pareto set and the ambiguity in the joint inversion problem increases.

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